

European objectives for the future climate model data research infrastructure

The mission and objectives of the European Network for Earth System Modelling (ENES) Climate Data Infrastructure (CDI).

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Introduction

The European Network for Earth System Modelling (ENES) has operated since 2001 to support advances in climate modelling and understanding¹. ENES has been supported by a succession of infrastructure projects (IS-ENES, IS-ENES2, and IS-ENES3; 2009-2022) as well as by an HPC Centre of Excellence (ESiWACE, ESiWACE2; 2015-2022). These activities, carried across multiple institutions exploiting mutual support, have been delivering on a community infrastructure strategy first published in 2012 and updated in 2017 [isenes2012, isenes2017]², and jointly deliver the ENES Research Infrastructure (ENES-RI).

The data service element, also known as the ENES Climate Data Infrastructure (ENES-CDI, Fig. 1), provides a range of services which are critical for the efficient exchange and exploitation of coordinated³ climate simulations which underpin major advances in climate science and decisions on social, political and economic adjustments associated with climate change.

This document outlines the overall objectives of the ENES climate data infrastructure, with some detail in terms of current activities, and near-term aspirations. It will be updated as the community infrastructure strategy evolves.

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¹ <https://portal.enes.org/community/about-enes>

² https://portal.enes.org/community/about-enes/the-future-of-enes/ENES_strategy_update_2017.pdf

³ The aim is to support activities which have been designed and deployed through a coordinated international effort to ensure that the outcomes are not only of scientific interest but also benefit from alignment with other international activities which can accelerate the pathways to impact.

General Objectives

Delivery of Data Services

To deliver a range of data curation and access services for the dissemination, analysis and preservation of climate simulations to support the scientists and institutions running and analysing climate simulations for international projects of European importance (such as WCRP coordinated experiments CMIP and CORDEX).

Expertise and Capability

To develop, maintain and deploy the expertise and capability which is needed to run our data services and to ensure that those services are integrated into European and global **digital infrastructures**. Support the staff as individuals and teams and work to ensure stability of resources. Develop, in collaboration with international partners, the services and systems required to meet the emerging challenges of handling multi-petabyte climate model output archives.

Promoting Trust in Climate Data Services

To implement and support the development and broader adoption of best practices in data documentation and management in order to create robust data services which deliver accessibility (of both results and their uncertainties) and enhance user trust in our services. Supply clear provenance information, transparency about assumptions and dependencies, reproducibility in our processing and discovery services, and guaranteed persistence of both data and the information and services necessary for the exploitation of data.

Specific Activities

A number of specific activities are required to deliver the general objectives and a common federated data infrastructure.

Delivery of Data Services

Supporting dissemination and exploitation of data generated through climate **simulations** by **Earth System Models** (ESMs). IS-ENES partners deliver data services supporting WCRP both through coordinated activities running an integrated service and through individual actions, typically supporting smaller projects, which exploit infrastructure and knowledge developed in the partnership.

- The coordinated data services focus on support for World Climate Research Programme (**WCRP**) activities, particularly CMIP and CORDEX archives;
- Service delivery is through the **Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF)** backed by data curation and management services at partner institutions, and related activities enhancing the planning, documentation, and support services for the CMIP and CORDEX archived;
- Support for downstream use of climate model output, particularly through partnership with the **Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC)** and the **Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S)**, is an important component of the services;
- Curation and dissemination of international reference data collections for the climate modelling science community;
- Critical services underpinning the work of the climate science community;
- Provide support and services for the climate impacts and other communities to facilitate exploitation of climate model data.

Expertise and Capability

We develop, maintain and deploy expertise and capability to run data services for climate model data from international collaborations, working with the international teams from the start of a project through to data dissemination

- We foster and support an international community with knowledge needed to manage and operate data services
- We realise a continuing development programme, which maintains and enhances systems and services:
 - Build interoperable services, conforming to and exploiting the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) initiative;
 - Develop scalable software tools;
 - Develop and deploy metadata and data standards supporting efficient and interoperable services, ensuring accurate communication of data and metadata, including provenance and citation information, and promote the adoption of standards to enhance the exchange of information between data providers, services and users.

Promoting Trust in Climate Data Services

We will commit to **Open Science**, to make the science of our community accessible to all levels of society, amateur or professional, and adopt and promote the principles of **FAIR Data**, to enhance the reusability of data. These principles run through all aspects of the ENES CDI work, and will be reflected in the following aims:

- Long-term archival ensuring that data and documentation of data is available and fully usable for at least 10 years, without any dependencies on continued support from scientists beyond the end of their research projects.
- Working through the World Climate Research Programme (**WCRP**) to establish globally recognised priorities.
- Transparency about the operation and governance of the infrastructure.
- Proactive engagement with data providers to ensure completeness of content in terms of documentation and quality control information.
- European and global international and **interdisciplinary** partnership supporting our mission.
- Assessment of detailed and informative user requirements through proactive engagement with user communities, developing and maintaining durable relationships to ensure effective communication between data service users and providers.
- Clear and functional citation mechanism to enable subsequent users to give measurable acknowledgement of the scientific work of data providers.
- Provenance information embedded in workflows and enabling reproducibility and providing transparency about the transformations performed.

Objectives and Activities

A full range of current ENES CDI activities funded, partially or completely, through the H2020 project IS-ENES3 will appear in the final version. Table 1 gives a few examples and comments on the objectives that they address.

Table 1: Activities mapped to objectives -- examples.

Activities	Objectives Addressed
<p>Operating the European nodes of the Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF) and contributing to governance and development efforts to maintain and improve the service.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Expertise and capability are enhanced through the close collaboration with international partners in the global federation. 2. ESGF is critical for the operation of data services for the major WCRP model intercomparison projects, the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP) and CORDEX. 3. Participation in ESGF creates trust and confidence by providing global visibility and deploying services which are agreed through international collaboration.
<p>Supporting the Climate and Forecast Conventions through moderation services, provision of community software tools and participation in community discussions.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Expertise and capability are enhanced through engagement with scientists working on data standards in other areas of climate science. 2. The CF Conventions form the foundations of the file metadata standards which ensure consistency in file contents and ensure that the data delivered meets user expectations. 3. Using a standard which is trusted and respected in a wider community ensures that our users know how to access and use information.
<p>CMIP6 Data Citation Service</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The data citation service gives users the information they need to provide accurate citation of the data that they have used. Data providers have, in the past, felt that the CMIP archive "hides" their ownership of data. The CMIP6 Data Citation Service ensures that the ENES CDI services comply with best practice and meet the FAIR2FAIR criteria for FAIR data, giving users clear and functional information about data provenance.

History and Current Status

The ENES CDI aligns and pools national services and resources to support the European climate research community. It also acts as a conduit for engagement with international partners outside Europe, including participation in the Earth System Grid Federation, bringing substantial additional benefits through global cooperation.

The CDI as it now exists was built from pre-existing national initiatives which were enhanced, made interoperable, and federated with support from further national funding and three EU projects of the InfraStructure for the European Network for Earth System modelling (IS-ENES) - namely IS-ENES (2009-2013), IS-ENES2 (2013-2017), and IS-ENES3 (2019-2022). National funding and income from Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) was used to sustain the operation of the infrastructure during the gap between IS-ENES2 and IS-ENES3. The CDI supports services for the C3S, which diversifies the funding base and mitigates the impact of fluctuations in research infrastructure funding and also enhances the dissemination of climate data curated and distributed by IS-ENES, reaching additional user communities.

The European Framework Programme funding covers a range of service development activities, both technical development and community engagement on joint requirements, and also contributes to service operation, particularly to aspects of service operation which have a clear international function and may be difficult to fund out of national operating budgets.

Through the period covered by the three IS-ENES projects, the scope of the integrating activities has been defined through the work plans developed and agreed by the ENES for each project and funded by the European Commission. Beyond IS-ENES3, this funding stream will no longer be available and service may need to be maintained with a more distributed portfolio of income sources. In order to maintain a clear understanding of what this major international activity is seeking to achieve, this paper seeks to set out a mission and objectives for the cooperative activities beyond 2022 which is independent of specific funding streams.

Appendix A: Glossary

Climate model: The term "climate model" here refers to numerical models used for quantitative **simulation** of the interactions of the important drivers of climate, including atmosphere, oceans, land surface, ice and parts of the biosphere. Climate models which include significant elements of the biosphere are often referred to as **Earth System Models** to distinguish them from climate models which use prescribed vegetation and only simulate the non-biological processes of the climate. The term General Circulation Model is used for climate models which include representations of the circulation in both atmosphere and oceans (also referred to as "coupled models", as in "coupled model intercomparison project").

Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S): C3S provides authoritative information about the past, present and future climate, as well as tools to enable climate change mitigation and adaptation strategies by policy makers and businesses. (<https://climate.copernicus.eu/>)

Digital Infrastructure (sometimes "e-infrastructure" or "cyberinfrastructure" [US]): "environments that support advanced data acquisition, data storage, data management, data integration, data mining, data visualisation and other computing and information processing services distributed over the Internet beyond the scope of a single institution." (<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cyberinfrastructure>)

Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF): A global international collaboration and digital infrastructure. [Williams et al. 2017].

Earth System Models (ESMs): Earth system models (ESMs) are climate models which combine atmosphere–ocean models with "models of other climate-related systems, such as the land surface, the cryosphere (glaciers, sea ice, and snow cover), hydrology (lakes, rivers, evaporation, and rainfall), and vegetation." (Edwards, 2010).

FAIR Data: The FAIR Data principles are a concise and measurable set of principles that are intended to act as a guideline for those wishing to enhance the reusability of their data holdings [wilkinsonetal]. The principles have been adopted and elaborated by **Force 11** [f11_fair], and their implementation is supported by **Go-FAIR**.

FORCE 11: "a community of scholars, librarians, archivists, publishers and research funders that has arisen organically to help facilitate the change toward improved knowledge creation and sharing." (<https://www.force11.org/about>)

Go-FAIR: An initiative from EU Member States (self-described as "bottom-up", but governed by ministerial representatives from participating EU countries) to promote the adoption of FAIR data principles. <https://www.go-fair.org>

Interdisciplinary refers simply to activities bridging the gaps between two or more academic disciplines, but usage can be confused. The wikipedia, for instance, includes Environmental Science in a list of academic disciplines, but goes on to describe it as an interdisciplinary activity. The UNESCO classification of fields of education [UNESCO_2013] uses the term interdisciplinary to refer to activities which cover several detailed fields (e.g. Earth Sciences and Environmental Sciences are both detailed fields, "climate" does not, unfortunately, enter into the 2013 UNESCO taxonomy of academic studies, either as a specific term or in any part of the discussion -- this means that climate science educational activities in EU Universities are completely invisible in official statistics). From a practical perspective, however, the climate

science community is working and functioning as a distinct discipline, and "**interdisciplinary**" in this document refers to interactions with functionally independent communities.

Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC): The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) is the United Nations body for assessing the science related to climate change. www.ipcc.ch

Open Science: "Open Science is a system change allowing for better science through open and collaborative ways of producing and sharing knowledge and data" (EC Open Science Fact Sheet) and is a policy priority for the European Commission (EC Open Science Policy). Often referred to as open scholarship or open research in the arts and humanities, it is a movement to make science accessible to all parts of society (Wikipedia).

Simulation: A simulation here refers to the execution of an experiment by a climate model.

WCRP: The World Climate Research Programme coordinates and facilitates international climate research to develop, share, and apply the climate knowledge that contributes to societal well-being. (<https://www.wcrp-climate.org/>)

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